

THE IMPORTANCE OF INDEPENDENT STUDY IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

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***Abstract.** This article is about independent study and its useful sides. Also. Implementing independent study in digital environment is clarified. examples of advantages for students are given: increasing motivation, self-confidence, critical thinking, saving time.*

***Keywords:** digital environment, independent study, independent study method, strategy, pandemic, digital system, simulation, self-control, cooperative education, small group discussion.*

One of the effective ways to develop the learning activity of students is independent study. There are a lot of ways to organize independent study which help it more successful. It is especially effective to design this in a digital environment. As a result of the COVID 19 pandemic in 2020, digital systems have entered every field in many developed countries of the world. Digital system is used, including in the field of education. First of all, it is appropriate to explain the meaning of the concepts of independent learning and digital learning environment. Independent study skills are the skills that help the learners to make their learning and studying process effective.[1] Independent learning is a skill that is not only related to learning, but more related to how the learning process is carried out. Independent learning activities shape learning activities that focus on students' awareness of learning and give students more freedom to independently determine how and what they want to learn. So, it can be said that this independent educational activity is closely related to the behavior of students in the implementation of their cognitive activities. Independent learning activity is the process of students conducting research within a certain topic and acquiring knowledge on their own. Independent education does not mean that students learn individually, but it is learning that requires students to learn independently. This independent study can help students determine learning goals, learning resources, the material they learn, and how they learn the learning material without being strictly regulated by the teacher. This can be done as a group or individually. Digital learning environment is a learning process organized using innovative technologies. According to Sh.Taneja, digital learning means when a person is imparting instructions to the students with the use of technology[2]. Furthermore, it is essential to clarify the term independent education method. The meaning of the independent education method is an equity learning strategy that is implemented individually or in groups. In its application, this method must be well managed by the teacher, who must go through a mature planning process. In terms of its implementation, this method refers to a mature level of preparation, coordinated implementation, as well as appropriate assessment of learning outcomes so that students achieve the expected standards of competence. Benefits of independent study in the digital environment:

1. Eliminates excessive paperwork. In the traditional form, independent study abstracts are carried out in the form of independent work slides. Also, in the digital learning environment, this is done online.

2. Saves students' time. Students do not have to wait in line in libraries to find information. It is not necessary for them to browse through many books and search for information. They have the necessary and unlimited information through the Internet.

3. Exchange of information. If students want to discuss a topic with each other, they can exchange messages with each other and give feedback on each other's work through social networks such as Telegram, Facebook, without leaving their homes. Through this, students get not only additional information. Maybe they will learn about their shortcomings.

4. Increases the ability to think independently. During independent learning activities, students also develop the ability to think freely. they distinguish which information is needed and which is necessary.

5. Increases interest. Usually, traditional lessons are standardized and can seem boring to students. In the digital learning environment, various video interactive games help to engage students in the learning process.

The most important part of the concept of an independent learning strategy is that each student should be able to determine which information sources are necessary to facilitate learning activities. Here are some self-study strategies:

Strategic study areas	Independent learning can be done at school, at home or in the library. To make this learning happen, students and teachers need to ensure that the learning environment used by students is comfortable and makes students more effective in learning. Thus, students can perform the learning process well.
Flexible study time	Independent study can be done at a time that suits the student. Each student has their own time table depending on their time availability.
Learning paths tailored by students	Every student has a learning style that works for them. Students who use the independent learning method should first determine what type they are. After that, it will be easier for him to determine the learning method that suits his situation and abilities.
Evaluation of educational results	Students do it themselves to evaluate learning outcomes. By comparing the learning objectives and the achieved results, students can learn the level of success.
Flexible learning pace	As for the student's pace of learning, it is determined by the student himself, which corresponds to the needs, abilities and opportunities of the student

Types of independent education methods

Regarding independent learning strategies that can be used according to Suryani[3], the following are among others:

Small group discussion

This method is one of the elements that help students to be active in the learning process. This method is used when students are asked to explore ideas, to summarize some important points, to improve students' skills and knowledge, to solve problems, and also when students want to review the topics learned the previous day.

Simulation

A simulation is a model that can bring real situations into the classroom. The advantages of this method are to change the appearance of students by practicing general skills, practicing special and team skills, developing problem-solving skills.

Discovery Learning

Explicit learning is a learning method that focuses on using available information. This method is useful in developing students' knowledge through independent learning.

Self-control

Self-directed learning is a process of learning that is initiated by individual students. The benefit of this method is to inform and empower students. If you are going to use it, then you have to make the assumption that students' ability depends on their ability to learn independently.

Cooperative Education

Cooperative learning is a group learning method designed by a teacher to solve a case or task. This method is useful for the formation of active learning habits of students, the formation of a sense of responsibility in students, as well as the development of communication and cooperation abilities and skills of students.

Contextual Instruction

Contextualized learning is a learning concept that helps teachers connect topics to real-life situations in everyday life. This method can encourage students to make connections between knowledge and its application in everyday life.

Project-based learning

Project-based learning is a learning method that uses project tasks as a means of learning activities to gain perspective, knowledge, and skills.

Challenging education

Problem-based learning is a method of learning that involves problems. In this regard, students have to search or dig for information to solve the problem.

Cooperative learning

Cooperative learning is a learning method that emphasizes cooperation between students and builds on the consensus that students develop. In this method, the teacher provides open-minded situations.

The advantages of using of independent learning methods in the course of educational activities.

In conclusion, independent study in digital environment are useful for students to gain knowledge. Students can improve their skills, can spend their time effectively. Also, teachers can have an opportunity to carry out their lessons efficiently.

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